

PCE-based Transport SDN Controller for Multi-Layer (Packet over Optical Flexi-Grid) Networks

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Abstract— To cope with the continuous demand of heterogeneous and larger data traffic volume, operators are seeking for effective solutions to accommodate such a demand in a flexible, agile, automatic and dynamic way. An appealing approach to face up that challenge focuses on deploying Multi-Layer Networks (MLN) to exploit the inherit benefits of both packet technologies and flexi-grid optical networks with Sliceable Bandwidth Variable Transceivers (SBVT). The aim is to leverage as much as possible the (electrical and optical) grooming chances fueled by such MLN when routing upcoming packet demands. The automatic control and configuration of the MLN infrastructure is driven by an implemented Transport SDN controller based on a Path Computation Element (PCE) architecture.

Besides describing the targeted MLN scenario, key features of the deployed T-SDN controller are presented. Next, it is also detailed an on-line devised MLN routing algorithm which is evaluated under dynamic heterogeneous data-rate packet demands. The performance evaluation considers two traffic models (Uniform and Non-Uniform) which are compared via two performance metrics: blocked bandwidth ratio and average setup delay.

Index Terms—Transport SDN controller, PCE, Multi-layer Networks, MPLS, Optical Flexi-Grid Networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE demand of cloud applications and services are drastically increasing the transport traffic needs, particularly for data center interconnection (e.g., dynamic storage at remotely geographic locations). Thus, network operators are seeking for solutions capable to not only deal with such necessities on the transport capacity (in an aggregated fashion) but also effective strategies being able to accommodate individual heterogeneous data rates (10, 40, or 100 Gb/s) imposing their own particular service requirements in terms of latency, availability, etc. Additionally, these services must be served dynamically, automatically and in an agile way aiming at attaining the most efficient use of the network resources [1].

A network scenario being currently adopted to address the above challenges and transport requirements focuses on tightly combining both packet and optical flexi-grid switching technologies [1]. This yields a Multi-Layer Network (MLN) infrastructure which leverages the best of both “worlds”: the

statistical multiplexing provided by packet switching (e.g., MPLS) and the coarse transport capacity provided by elastic optical networks relying on Bandwidth-Variable Optical Cross Connects (BV-OXC) and Sliceable Bandwidth Variable Transceivers (SBVT) devices [2].

In the targeted MLN, one of the most appealing features is the capability to exploit the advantages brought by both electrical and optical traffic grooming strategies [3]. For the sake of clarification, (traditional) electrical grooming allows transporting multiple packet traffic flows into exiting lower-layer (optical) channels. Indeed, established optical channels become virtual packet links forming a Virtual Network Topology (VNT). The unused bandwidth of these virtual links can be then used when computing and serving upcoming packet connection demands. This yields valuable benefits in terms of more efficient use of the client layer ports as well the optical capacity. Similar aims are provided by the so-called optical grooming which is only performed if SBVTs are deployed. The basic principle of optical grooming is to allow offloading the electronic processing burden towards the optical layer. This does also enhance the transponder and optical spectrum utilization (e.g., guard bands between neighboring optical flows are removed). In a nutshell, optical grooming enables that a set of optical flows from/to different sources/destinations are groomed using sub-transceivers into a given SBVT [1][3].

The automation and programmability of the MLN accommodating (in real time) services with different traffic data rates and requirements is provided by a unified Transport Software Defined Networking (T-SDN) controller [4]. T-SDN controller in fact scopes any technology below IP (e.g., MPLS and optical flexi-grid) to transport traffic in a connection-oriented way. This provides advantages such as the control simplification, multi-vendor integration, agile and flexible configuration, open and standard interfaces, etc. Herein, the implementation of the T-SDN controller follows the architecture described in [4] which extends the functionalities of the Path Computation Element (PCE) and its protocol interface (PCEP) to not only compute and instantiate connections but also configuring paths’ network elements (NE): BV-OXC, MPLS switches and SBVTs [5]. This solution is

referred to as PCE Central Controller (PCECC) [4][5].

Upon receiving a packet connection, the T-SDN controller triggers a MLN routing algorithm exploiting both electrical and optical grooming opportunities using the current MLN topology (i.e., physical and virtual links) and network resources: packet link bandwidth, optical spectrum, packet ports and SBVTs. This work details the implementation of the T-SDN controller for MLN as well as the conceived routing algorithm to dynamically compute, configure, modify and release packet flows requesting different data traffic rates.

The remainder of this paper describes the targeted MLN infrastructure along with choices to realize electrical and optical grooming (Section II). Section III describes the implemented T-SDN controller and the devised MLN routing algorithm. Section IV focuses on the attained experimental performance evaluation under dynamic traffic considering as figures of merit the bandwidth blocked ratio and the average setup delay.

II. MULTI-LAYER (PACKET OVER FLEXI-GRID) NETWORK

Figure 1 depicts the considered MLN where packet nodes (A, B, C and D) are connected to SBVTs bound to particular BV-OXCs. Packet NEs are equipped with p client ports operating at a given data rate. In the example client ports (p : 1) operate at 400 Gb/s. SBVTs are made up of a pool of N sub-transponders allowing generating up to N different optical flows. Each optical flow occupies an optical frequency slot (FS) which is determined by a central frequency (e.g., 193.1 GHz) and a slot width (e.g. multiple of 12.5 GHz). Every sub-transponder operates at a fixed symbol rate (e.g., 25 Gbauds) supporting different modulation formats (e.g., DP-QPSK, DP-8QAM, DP-16QAM). The selection of the modulation formats enables flexible data rates per optical flow depending on the maximum distance supported by each modulation format.

In the example, $r1$ demands a connection between B and C of 100 Gb/s. To satisfy $r1$, a flexi-grid connection is allocated between B and C configuring their respective sub-transponders to DP-8QAM (6 bits/symbol). Thereby, in the considered example, the established optical flow supports 25 Gbauds \times 6 bits/symbol, i.e., 150 Gb/s. In a MLN, all optical flows become virtual links (i.e., Vlink) at the packet layer between a pair of packet nodes (e.g., B and C). The TE properties of the Vlink are inherited from its underlying optical flow: i) TE metric (based on the number of traversed optical NEs) and maximum reservable bandwidth (maxRsvBw) derived from the SBVT configuration (i.e., 150 Gb/s). Since $r1$ requested 100 Gb/s, 50 Gb/s are still unused in the created Vlink which could be used by another upcoming request thanks to electrical grooming.

A new request $r2$ between B and A is received for 10 Gb/s. It is assumed that due to the computed path distance uniquely DP-QPSK can be chosen (25 Gbauds \times 4 bits/symbol, i.e., 100 Gb/s). As above, a new Vlink is created between B and A NEs. After setting up $r2$, there is still 90 Gb/s unused for future electrical grooming decisions. Observe that optical flows supporting both $r1$ and $r2$ are groomed at the optical layer. That is, 2 different sub-transponders for independent optical flows within the same SBVT are occupied [3]. Both packet connections arrive to the SBVT via the same client port. This

indeed reflects one of the key benefits of optical grooming, i.e. offloading the packet layer. In other words, optical grooming is attained without requiring different client ports per packet demand. The benefit of optical grooming can be achieved at both source and/or destination SBVTs. In this regard, when $r3$ (between D and C) is set up $r1$ and $r3$ associated optical flows are groomed into the same destination SBVT attached to NE C.

In summary, in the targeted MLN the aim is to dynamically serve as much heterogeneous packet requests as possible taking advantage of the both electrical and optical grooming opportunities.

Fig. 1. MLN integrating packet and optical flexi-grid switches with SBVTs.

III. TRANSPORT SDN (T-SDN) ARCHITECTURE FOR MLN

Figure 2.a) shows the implemented architecture of the PCE-based T-SDN controller for handling the MLN. The core building block is the PCECC [4] which performs three basic functions: i) to process packet connections requests arriving via a NorthBound Interface (NBI) using a PCEP API. Each request specifies (see step 0 in Fig. 3) packet endpoints and bandwidth (bits/s); ii) to perform path computation for received new packet demands specifying packet endpoints and required bandwidth (in Gb/s); iii) to handle the Provisioning Manager function for configuring NEs (packet and optical nodes as well as SBVTs) to set up/release packet and optical connections.

Path Computation executes a devised MLN routing algorithm (step 1 in Fig. 2.b). It uses the Traffic Engineering Database (TED) information (topology and network resources) updated by the Topology Manager (i.e., via BGP-LS with proposed extensions). The output of the Path Computation is encoded as N ($=> I$) Explicit Route Objects (EROs) describing the entire MLN path (i.e., nodes, links and network resources). One of these EROs is dedicated to the so-called Client Layer (packet) ERO which besides carrying the packet nodes and links contains the selected label (from the MPLS Label database). It is worth outlining that each packet connection uses the same common MPLS label in every path (physical or virtual) link. Each packet connection allocates a different MPLS label. If $N > I$, the remaining EROs belong to the Server Layer (i.e. optical flexi-grid). Such EROs are related to optical path segments [5] (nodes, links, FS and SBVTs) Each server layer connection induces a packet Vlink.

Both Client and Server Layer EROs are passed to the Provisioning Manager function. This operates as an Active Stateful PCE [6] storing existing (packet and optical) connections in the LSP database (LSPDB), and programming involved NEs via PCLabelUpd [5] (steps 5 and 8 in Fig. 2.b).

To manage (e.g., setting up) each optical path segment, the Provisioning Manager relies on a standalone process referred to as Virtual Network Topology Manager (VNTM). VNTM is responsible for: i) retrieving link identifiers for the new virtual link. To do this, the VNTM communicates with the respective packet NE's Agents connected by the virtual link using a proprietary TCP protocol (step 3); ii) requesting to the Provisioning Manager (PCEP PCInitiate / PCRpt, in step 4) the allocation/removal of optical resources such as frequency slot and SBVT (transceivers) specified in the Server Layer ERO; iii) triggering the virtual link creation (via the proprietary TCP protocol, step 6) including all its TE properties (metric and available bandwidth) to the respective packet NEs' Agents. Finally, iv) VNTM occupies / releases the used bandwidth (reflecting the SBVT configuration) in the physical ports of the virtual link's NEs (step 6 in Fig. 2.b)).

When a Vlink is created / modified / removed (step 6 and 9), its respective packet NEs' Agents send a BGP Update message. Indeed, all NEs' Agent keep track of their own local resources being responsible for its configuration / dissemination. Link state information is stored by the Topology Manager in the TED for subsequent path computations. Herein, we consider that whenever a new Vlink is created the establishment of the packet connection over that link is arbitrarily delayed 5s. This ensures that the Vlink is completely configured prior to proceed with the actual programmability of the packet connection.

A. Traffic Grooming Algorithm

The devised on-line MLN routing algorithm aims at applying both electrical and optical grooming strategies to attain the most efficient use of MLN resources and is formed by 2 independent Steps.

Step 1 routes a request, using a shortest path cost (SP), only over existing packet VNT to favor electrical grooming. If it succeeds, the computed Client Layer ERO is delivered to the Provisioning Manager. Otherwise, Step 2 is executed.

Step 2 triggers a MLN routing combining packet ports, virtual and physical optical links and SBVTs. SBVTs support different modulation formats (DP-16QAM, DP-8QAM, DP-QPSK). The algorithm prioritizes selecting the most advanced modulation format (MF) as long as the maximum permitted distance (in km) is not exceeded. Bearing this in mind, supported MF s are sorted in decreasing order (bits/symbol), and the SP is executed for each candidate MF . If a path is found, this is passed to the Provisioning Manager. Otherwise, next MF is explored. For a considered MF , the required number of transceivers (NTr) in a SBVT is computed to support the requested bandwidth (r). Using NTr , the fixed symbol rate (S) and MF (bits/symbol), it is computed the so-called "optical" bandwidth (OBw). In general, $OBw (NTr * S * MF) \geq r$.

During the SP execution (path tree construction), for each eligible link (packet or optical) a set of restrictions are checked. Specifically, for both physical packet ports and Vlinks, it is checked that the computed OBw can be occupied. If not, the packet link / port is discarded. The cost of allocating OBw in a physical port is set to 1, whereas in a Vlink such a cost is matched to the TE metric computed when creating the Vlink. In

this work, this cost is set to $max \{1, number\ of\ optical\ hops - 3\}$.

For a candidate optical link (between a pair of BV-OXCs) its cost is always set to 1. To add an optical link to the SP it must be verified that: i) the spectrum continuity and contiguity constraints are ensured [5]; ii) the maximum distance permitted for the considered MF is not exceeded. If either i) or ii) are not satisfied, the optical link is discarded. Finally, the allocation of NTr in a SBVT has also an implicit cost to be accounted. Particularly, if a SBVT where the NTr to be occupied is already being used by another optical flow, the cost of allocating sub-transponder in that SBVT is set to 1 to promote optical grooming. Otherwise, the it is set to 2.

The output path may traverse different optical segments (using NTr in SBVTs) and Vlinks. If no path is found for all MF s, the connection is blocked. Otherwise, Client and Server Layer EROs are sent to the Provisioning Manager.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

A. Validation of T-SDN Interfaces and Protocols

Fig. 2.c depicts the PCEP messages captured at PCECC for setting up a new packet connection. Upon receiving a PCInitiate message sent through the NBI PCEP API, the MLN path is computed. For each new Vlink, derived from the computed path, the VNTM invokes the Provisioning Manager (PCInitiate) to establish their associated Server Layer/s (optical segment/s). This entails programming involved optical NEs (PCLabelUpd). To avoid convergence issues, the actual packet connection configuration (PCInitiate / PCLabelUpd) is delayed 5s, ensuring that the optical segment/s and Vlink/s are actually set up and created. Finally, a PCRpt is sent through the NBI to report that the connection is active. Interactions via proprietary TCP protocol and BGP Updates are not shown due to the space limitations. Nevertheless, it is worth mentioning that BGP Update messages have been extended to carry within standard Path Attribute Link State details about supported link switching technology (packet or optical flexi-grid).

B. Performance Evaluation and Future Work

The performance evaluates the entire system (T-SDN controller and MLN routing algorithm) under dynamic packet traffic with heterogeneous data rates and models (Uniform vs. Non-Uniform). Packet connection arrival process is Poisson (mean inter-arrival time is 20s) and the duration (holding time, HT) is exponentially modelled where mean HT is varied. For each HT data point, 4000 connections are generated. Uniform model considers that 10, 40 and 100 Gb/s connection requests are uniformly demanded. Non-Uniform considers 10, 40 and 100 Gb/s data rates generated with a proportion of 6:3:1. Fig. 3.a shows the MLN topology: 14 MPLS NEs connected via SBVTs to 14 BV-OXCs forming an optical mesh network. MPLS NEs are equipped with a single 400 Gb/s port. Each SBVT supports 3 MFs (DP-QPSK, DP-8QAM, DP-16-QAM) having 10 transceivers. SBVT's features (fixed symbol rate and maximum distance per MF) are detailed in Fig. 3.a along with optical link distance (km). Optical links support 128 NCFs.

Fig. 2: a) PCE-based T-SDN Architecture for MLN; b) Workflow for setting up a packet connection; c) PCEP messages for setting up Server and Client EROs.

Fig. 3.b plots the bandwidth blocked ratio versus the HT for Uniform and Non-uniform models. As HT increases, blocked bandwidth degrades since resources become more used which complicates finding a feasible path. In this regard, the most limiting network resource is packet port. Indeed, when a new optical segment (part of a MLN path) is being set up, occupied port bandwidth is OBw . Recall that OBw is related to the SBVT configuration. Therefore, OBw gets bandwidth values (100, 150, 200Gb/s, Fig. 1.c) larger than the requested packet connection's bandwidth, i.e., r . Thereby, port bandwidth is exhausted faster than other resources (e.g., optical spectrum and SBVT) as HT grows. In light of this, grooming traffic flows becomes crucial to optimize port bandwidth usage. This fact is better appreciated observing that Non-Uniform traffic does lower blocked bandwidth compared to Uniform. The reason behind that is that in Non-Uniform, low- and medium-rate requests (10-40 Gb/s) are proportionally larger than high-rate demands. Thus, chances to groom that connections into existing virtual topology (using unused port's bandwidth, OBw) are more likely to occur than in Uniform model. Hence, in the Non-Uniform the number of established demands are higher increasing in turn the served bandwidth

Fig. 3.c plots the average setup delay versus the HT for both Uniform and Non-uniform models. We observe that as HT is increased (i.e., connections last more time in the network increasing the instantaneous data traffic), in general, the average setup delay is lowered. Indeed, in MLN, higher traffic induces larger number of co-existing Vlinks (VNT). Consequently, the VNT is higher connected and meshed which favors adopting more grooming decisions. This effect is reflected in the average setup delay as well. Specifically, when serving a new request, the existing VNT allows reducing the need for new Vlinks (and their associated optical flows). Thereby, the forced (by policy) delay of 5s to guarantee that a

Fig. 3: a) MLN Topology and SBVT capabilities; b) Bandwidth Blocked Ratio vs HT; c) Average Setup Delay vs HT.

Vlink is created before routing a packet demand is less needed. Thus, this does lower the setup delay. Finally, observe that lowering the average setup delay when increasing the HT is more appreciated in the Non-Uniform than in the Uniform model. In the Non-Uniform model low rate packet requests have higher occurrence and, hence grooming opportunities into the VNT are more likely to happen than in the Uniform model.

Future work will focus on conducting and obtaining more exhaustive results varying some scenario parameters such as the number of client ports, SBVT's sub-transponders, etc., as well as investigating the effect of modifying the policy of 5s delay, different traffic generation values, etc. Last but not least, an interesting metric to be measured is the incurred control overhead (PCEP, BGP-LS, TCP) vs. the generated traffic to assess the scalability of the whole system.

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